

Back

Demand - #123

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- Request History
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Request Type

Audit Demand

Protocol number

6798

Subject Area

Regulation

Sphere

Federal

National Audit System Component

Type of Receipt

Date received

08/06/2022

Forecast of service in the unit

08/06/2022

Protocol number

2193814217401

Admissibility Criteria

Draft automatically saved

Activity already done or planned? No

Search in 1CP

Details

County

Evidence of irregularity

Period

Documents of irregularity

Application attachments

Generic request?

Subject of the demand

Applicant

Macro Claimant

Information

Origin of the demand

Claimant's deadline (in days)

Entry date

Turnaround time

Demand Type

Ordinary Demand

Complexity

Macro Claimant

Competence

Sim

Materiality

Relevance

Opportunity

Analysis Conclusions

Accomplish demand? Yes

Justification (reason)

Cancel

Send